

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: National Oceanography Centre

Towards a Deeper Understanding of
Eddies using Machine Learning

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

Understanding ocean dynamics is critical for the scientific community as it has a direct impact on climate change and the functioning of marine ecosystems. One of the key aspects of ocean sciences lies in the understanding of eddies as they play a significant role in transferring energy and nutrients across the ocean [1]. On a global scale, the movement of eddies accounts for approximately 90% of the ocean's kinetic energy, and they are known to affect ocean dynamics, weather conditions and commercial activities [2]. Eddies are also explicitly linked to climate change, playing a crucial role in the deep storage of carbon and heat, whilst long-term shifts in poleward eddy activity are indicative of a warming climate. As a result, being able to track and detect eddies is crucial for physical oceanographers in not only understanding eddies but also in accurately modelling the changing oceans and climate.

Being able to detect and track the movement of eddies is also vital in gathering data on eddies. Oceanographers who wish to study the depth profiles of eddies collect data by crossing through them with aquatic robots such as gliders or autonomous underwater vehicles, measuring temperature-salinity and other parameters which describe their behaviour and transport properties. For other studies, knowing the locations of eddies can help pilots avoid getting stuck in them or use them to their advantage by using the currents to increase the endurance of glider missions.

However, detecting eddies is non-trivial due to their complex dynamics. Traditionally, eddies were detected using spatio-temporal data collected using satellite remote sensing. According to the direction in which they rotate, eddies can cause significant upwelling or downwelling which leaves strong signatures in sea surface height (SSH) which are detectable using gridded satellite altimetry products. Such gridded products involve interpolating sparse sea surface height observations from a constellation of orbiting satellites onto a regular latitude-longitude grid using optimal interpolation (OI). OI [3] is a widely used method of data assimilation that provides an estimate for the current sea surface height via a weighted least squares fit to observations. The weights in OI

are the inverse of the error covariance matrices for the observations and the background field.

With access to a gridded SSH map, most studies then rely on an automatic detection algorithm that identifies and tracks the eddies. These methods can be typically divided into parameter-based models and more recently, machine learning-based approaches. Parameter or model-based methods typically look for maxima and minima in sea-level anomaly maps, defined as the difference between the current SSH minus a 5-month moving average, before forming a closed contour around the extremum. Machine learning methods on the other hand often adopt approaches from computer vision such as image segmentation or object detection algorithms. Currently, the most used approach is to use software called py-eddy tracker (PET) which is a model-based approach that iteratively builds eddies under a set of rule-based conditions.

However, there is an open question as to how well current eddy detection methods work. Firstly, global gridded SSH maps which are used to detect eddies are only provided at $1/4^\circ$ resolution (30 km grid spacing). At these scales, unresolved eddies have been shown to introduce aliasing effects that distort the characterisation of larger eddies, resulting in the underestimation of smaller eddies and the overestimation of larger ones. To put things in perspective, the size of mesoscale eddies ranges from 5 to 200 km. Indeed, it has been shown that satellite-derived products capture roughly 6% of actual eddies in the North Atlantic [4]. Consequently, these flaws in altimetry-based products have a significant impact on downstream scientific research. There exist many studies that have used altimeter data to make inferences on eddy properties, relate eddies to other ocean variables, and estimate surface eddy kinetic energy. In all cases, the results must therefore be treated with caution given most of the eddy field is missed and surviving parts are likely to be affected by noise and aliasing.

Further detecting eddies from SSH maps using machine learning is also tricky. With very few labelled examples, machine learning approaches have often been hindered by a lack of high-quality data, tending to use extensive data augmentation or training on the outputs of PET. Training on the outputs of PET, however, is problematic as the machine learning algorithm will try to learn the biases and shortcomings of PET.

Model-based methods are also prone to errors, requiring one to define a strict set of criteria that must be satisfied in order to classify an eddy. This can lead to eddies being erroneously split into separate vortices and model-based detection algorithms being sensitive to observation noise. Further, eddies are also prone to disappearing before reappearing again, making it hard to ensure the temporal consistency of eddy paths. In the above context, the aim of this Data Study Group (DSG) challenge is to improve how we can detect and track eddies using machine learning. In this DSG challenge, we investigate how to apply machine learning and deep learning models to automatically extract higher-level features and identify eddies from satellite Sea Surface Height data (SSH).

1.2 Main objectives

With the advancement of machine learning, computing power, and large-scale data handling capabilities, the ability to analyse complex spatio-temporal data has increased. Leveraging machine learning techniques to learn patterns and features from large datasets will improve the accuracy in the identification and tracking of eddies. With such motivation, we formulate two objectives: (A) SSH mapping and (B) eddy identification. Accordingly, the following two research questions were posed, forming the two directions of work (A and B) during the DSG challenge.

1.2.1 Objective A: SSH Mapping

The key research question to be addressed in this task is as follows: how can we accurately map SSH onto a high-resolution grid given a set of sparse satellite observations using machine learning? The current resolution of the global gridded SSH maps is $1/4^\circ$ (30 km grid spacing). As the mesoscale eddies typically range from 5 to 200 km, such sparseness in the SSH maps leads to the underestimation of smaller eddies and the overestimation of larger ones. From this perspective, in this task, we will be using such sparse satellite observations ($1/4^\circ$) to map the SSH to a high-resolution grid that is at $1/60^\circ$ resolution using machine learning techniques.

1.2.2 Objective B: Eddy Identification

The main research question to be addressed in this task is as follows: How can we effectively detect eddies given an SSH map using machine learning algorithms? For this part, we aim to investigate different deep learning methods to effectively identify eddies from low-resolution data with limited labelled samples. Furthermore, we will explore the ability to apply data augmentation to enhance the model training and improve performance.

Bringing streams (A) and (B) together in the end, we attempt to create a single pipeline taking in sparse data, mapping it to a high-resolution grid and identifying eddies accurately and reliably in real-time end-to-end.

1.3 Approach

For both tasks A and B, i.e., SSH mapping and eddy identification, we conducted a literature review of various machine learning architectures relevant to the field ranging from semi-supervised learning methods, Gaussian processes, and Convolutional Neural Networks. More specifically, for SSH mapping (Task A), we adopted a physics-informed neural network by utilising the Helmholtz equation as an additional loss function in addition to autoencoders and simple CNN architectures. For the eddy identification (Task B), the Mask-Region Convolutional Neural Networks (RCNN) architecture is used.

2 Data overview

Arguably, the biggest hindrance to improved SSH mapping and eddy detection is the lack of an accurate high-resolution ground truth field. Recently, there have been significant advances in large Ocean General Circulation Models (OGCMs) which resolve currents at very high resolutions. As a result, these models have been used increasingly as a proxy for high-resolution ground truth data such as SSH.

In this DSG challenge, we worked with three different datasets: The eNATL60 provided by the challenge comprising the high fidelity simulations on the North Atlantic Ocean obtained. The simulations were

performed with NEMO ocean model over the North Atlantic at $1/60^\circ$ grid resolution. The SSH maps were generated by interpolating the eNATL60 model onto real satellite tracks. The data cover the period from 2010-06-30 to 2020-09-01. And then, we used the publicly available py-eddy-tracker dataset (PET14) for the SSH mapping. And for the eddy identification, we used the SSH AVISO maps and their corresponding segmentation masks 2000-2010 (4 Go)) / Test data 2011 dataset (200 Mo).

2.1 Dataset description

For the SSH mapping task A, along with the provided dataset, we also explore the publicly available py-eddy-tracker (PET14) dataset [5] for the Southern Atlantic Ocean region; this data is generated using a py-eddy-tracker SSH-based approach. It consists of daily data for 15 years (1998 to 2012). We used ten years of data from 2000 to 2010, which makes up to 4018 data samples, where each sample includes an SSH image of size (168, 168) Pixels and a resolution of 0.24 along with SSH segmentation map that shows the eddies. As appears in this dataset, one eddy can last from several days to more than a year. Figure 1 describes statistical details of the average, maximum, and minimum number of eddies that appear in a single day and the number of new eddies that occur daily.

For the eddy identification, we used the SSH AVISO maps used by the Python package EddyNet [6]. The dataset is from gridded L4 daily SSH fields as distributed by CMEMS (formerly distributed by AVISO+) with a horizontal resolution of 0.25° and a daily temporal resolution. A subregion of the Southern Atlantic Ocean (SAO) of a 48° height and a 64° width. The images have a size of 192×256 pixels. The dataset spans a total of 12 years, ranging from 2000 to 2011. We used a second dataset publicly available in the GitHub repository of EddyNet. The training of a mask-RCNN consisted of 4,018 SSH maps for training and 365 for testing. The unlabeled dataset that we generated from the eNATL60 dataset for the semi-supervised approach from the same region as the EddyNet dataset has 3,288 SSH maps (7 extra maps for each map). We then augmented this dataset to 26,304 SSH maps. All the maps were 168×168 in size.

Figure 1: Statistics of the EddyNet dataset, The average, minimum, and maximum number of eddies per day and the number of new eddies that occur per day.

2.2 Data quality issues

It is reported that only 6% of true eddies are detected in the North Atlantic [4], and are from low-resolution products. Most of the eddies in the ocean have spatial scales that cannot be resolved by gridded products with a resolution of 0.25 degrees. Furthermore, unresolved eddies introduce aliasing that distorts the identification and characterisation of larger eddies.

Currently, there are very few labelled eddy datasets, making machine learning applications difficult. Also, these models are prone to errors due to hard-coded criteria that make them sensitive to noise. On the other hand, when applying a more general ML approach, the small size of the training set makes them very prone to overfitting.

2.3 Data visualisation

The baseline data that we start with for SSH mapping and the eventual eddy detection are the along-track measurements obtained from traditional altimetry satellites. The along-track SSH measurements can be plotted and visualised as shown on the left-hand side of Figure 2. The corresponding SSH map from the same coordinates as the along-track data is shown on the right-hand side of Figure 2.

Figure 2: Example of one image from the eNATL60 dataset (ALTIKA from September 2020). The left side of the image shows the along-track measurements and the right side image shows the corresponding map.

There are different approaches to interpolating the data into a grid to generate the SSH map, such as inverse distance weighting (IDW), radial basis function (RBF), and Universal Kriging. The results of the SSH maps using the above approaches are shown in Figure 3

An SSH map is labelled by annotating square by square (the equivalent of pixel by pixel) whether it is part of an eddy or not. Such square-by-square annotations of an image are its masks. These masks can be used for training an ML segmentation model; see Figure 4.

Figure 3: Example of different interpolation approaches for the SSH maps.

Figure 4: Example of the mask of an SSH map from the EddyNet dataset.

3 Experiments

3.1 Exploration and Selection of Machine Learning Approaches

During the initial phase of the DSG challenge, we explored a range of potential machine learning architectures for our intended tasks. We summarise them here briefly while emphasising their relevance for the current DSG project. In Table 1, we list all the models.

Model	Task	Used/explored
Reinforcement Learning	SSH-Mapping	Explored but not used due to time limit
Diffusion models	SSH-Mapping	Explored but results are not presented due to time limit and incompleteness
Neural Processes	SSH-Mapping	Explored but not used due to time limit
AutoEncoders	SSH-Mapping	Explored and used
Vector-field modelling	SSH-Mapping	Explored and used
Physics-informed NN	SSH-Mapping	Explored and used
CNN	SSH-Mapping	Explored and used
Mask-RCNN	Eddy Identification (Semantic Segmentation)	Explored and used
LSTM + CNN	Eddy Identification (Sequential Image Analysis)	Explored and used

Table 1: List of different approaches considered and used for tackling each task of the project.

3.1.1 SSH Mapping

Reinforcement learning: A few reinforcement learning (RL) methods have been used with Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) for inpainting, i.e., restoration of missing parts of a picture [7, 8, 9]. Some characteristics of general RL methods are summarised here: They would need to set up an agent with a continuous action space and multi-actions. Stable-baseline package has pre-designed models (but not pre-trained). It can be quite time-consuming to train RL models. RL is still not efficient for sparse state spaces and rewards [10]. Hierarchical RL architectures are promising in the context that two or more RL agents work together on the same task while one manages the high-level features with the other focusing on more in-depth analysis [11]. In the current work, we did not use RL techniques due to their computational time and the scope of the current DSG challenge.

Diffusion Models: Diffusion models regularly outperform other generative models like GANs [12]. One of the advantages of diffusion models for our applications is the high latent dimensionality corresponding to our data. However, they are equally prone to hallucinating features. Whereby, if we are to use the diffusion model to interpolate the sparse data, this resulting map might look very realistic. However, it would be very hard to identify whether this corresponds to the physical reality in the actual SSH maps. One approach to remedy this would be to ground the diffusion model using the available physics of the problem. Domain-specific advances on this have been made [13] to address some of the problems, albeit not on recognising when the model is hallucinating. As of the time of this report, the authors are not aware of any broadly implemented algorithm. Hence, the development would be outside the scope of this DSG. Furthermore, given how computational and time-expensive the diffusion models are, it was decided that this would clash with both the scope of the DSG as well as the real-time application of the SSH mapping application.

Neural Processes: Models based on neural processes are especially good at time series and interpolation data prediction with uncertainty measures, giving a massive advantage over the shortcomings of diffusion models. Neural processes combine the advantage of Gaussian Processes (GP) and Neural Networks (NN) [14]. Similar to GPs, they

define distributions over functions and can estimate the uncertainty in their predictions. Neural Processes are also computationally efficient like NNs but also learn to adapt their priors to data. While such approaches can be relevant to the current work, we did not manage to explore the full potential due to the time limitations of the project.

AutoEncoders: Unlike diffusion models, autoencoders (AE) adopt a low-dimensional representation of the latent space. Variational AutoEncoders (VAE), introduce variational inference to the model and regularise the latent space. We have utilised traditional and variational autoencoders for the SSH interpolation and the results are presented in Section 3.

Vector-Field Modelling: There are research studies where satellite-measured SST images are used to obtain data on the characteristics of oceanic eddies. For instance, an automated eddy detection approach was developed using a velocity-geometry eddy detection scheme [15]. An edge detection scheme [16] was used to automatically detect eddies in the Gulf Stream [17]. Another method involved the combination of edge detection and flow fields between two consecutive SST images [18]. Eddy analysis from the SST field is performed through the following steps: first, a thermal-wind velocity field is derived; second, an automated detection method is applied; and finally, eddy tracks are reconstructed.

Mesoscale eddies (with diameters ranging from 50 to 250 km) are routinely detected by Eulerian methods using satellite altimetry measurements of sea surface height (SSH). Eddies may be identified as regions filled with closed streamlines of the SSH field (e.g. [19, 20, 21]) or as features obtained from a wavelet-packet decomposition of the SSH field [22, 23, 24]. Virtual force fields have been used to analyze eddy detection. According to these studies, the method involved an excessive number of parameters affecting the outcome [25]. Eddies with diameters of hundreds of kilometers were detected using velocity fields and optical flow algorithms. Those methods cannot be used in the present case since the vectors derived from those methods are too irregular due to the small temperature gradients. Despite the fact that optical flow algorithms do not allow smooth velocity fields to be extracted, eddies are better defined by the modulus of velocity field images than by brightness in temperature

maps. Consequently, the modulus of the velocity fields is used in those studies to obtain a binary image of the brightness temperature map.

Physics-informed Neural Networks: After we determined that diffusion models were too computationally expensive to investigate during the DSG, and after seeing the promising initial results from the vector fields, we decided to look into how to utilise the underlying physical information with a deep learning technique, which is termed as Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINN) [26].

In this work, our main objective is to generate a velocity vector field from the SSH dataset. We then combine the velocity field information with a PINN by integrating the physical governing equation into the loss function of the neural network. We set a simple regression neural network in the form of a simple multi-layer perceptron model. We implemented the model by deriving the vector fields from the output of this model and using the comparison between this and the target vector fields as part of the loss function, thereby effectively including the Helmholtz equation as part of the loss function. We could use the divergence-free Helmholtz equation (or the curl or transverse part of the Helmholtz decomposition) due to the divergence component primarily affecting small processes, not larger scale processes like the mesoscale eddies. The equation implies that vorticity in the flow field is divergence-free given by the following equation: $\nabla \cdot (\nabla \times V) = 0$.

To achieve such PINN models we need the velocity vector fields, which we were able to calculate using the contour images. As a result, we have a global vector field in which each cell of the grid has an assigned vector. After that we have the complete vector field in hand, following which critical points can be characterized according to the behavior of nearby tangent curves. By knowing the location and classification of critical points in a vector field, the topology of the field is known in small areas around these. The critical points are classified based on the vector field around these points using the eigenvalues and the eigenvectors of the Jacobian matrix. The structures in Figure 5 are the three types of critical points that resemble the structure of eddies. From the initial dataset, the overall path for generating vector fields is framed in Figure 6.

Convolutional Neural Networks: Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are good at recognising patterns and are less computationally expensive

Figure 5: The structure of three types of critical points of vector fields that resemble the structure of Eddies.

Figure 6: From a sparse SSH dataset to generating vector fields and identifying and categorizing critical points.

than an equivalent depth MLP /Fully Connected Network. We use CNNs to perform the SSH image interpolation from the Along Track data. It can be thought of as a regression task, where the Along Track data as input is used to predict the pixel values for the SSH grid. The results are presented in Section 3.

3.1.2 Eddy Identification

After obtaining the high-resolution SSH maps from task A, in task B we need to analyse them to identify the eddies. The creation of such a model would allow for the tracking and prediction of eddies occurrence in the future. We explored the following methods for eddy identification.

Semantic segmentation is a computer vision technique that involves dividing an image into multiple segments or regions and assigning a class label to each segment based on its semantic meaning. In other words, it

Figure 7: The approaches implemented for eddy identification.

involves identifying and labelling different objects or regions within an image. In our case, we want to apply semantic segmentation to identify and detect the location of eddies in SSH map images. This involves detecting and labelling each pixel in the image that belongs to an eddy region, allowing us to analyse the distribution and movement of eddies in the ocean.

For semantic segmentation, Convolutional neural networks (CNN) have been extensively used in the field of image recognition and processing for image classification. When there is more than one type of object or for more complicated images, more complex architectures are needed. Mask R-CNN [27] is a state-of-the-art extension of the popular Faster R-CNN [28] object detection model, which adds an additional branch to the network for predicting object masks in addition to object-bounding boxes and class labels. Mask R-CNN works by first generating region proposals, or candidate object bounding boxes, in the input image using a Region Proposal Network (RPN). Then, for each region proposal, the network extracts a fixed-length feature vector using a Region of Interest (RoI) pooling layer. The network then uses two parallel branches to predict the class label and bounding box coordinates for each object within the region proposal, as well as a binary mask indicating the pixel-level segmentation of the object within the region. The mask branch is implemented as a small Fully Convolutional Network (FCN) that takes the RoI-pooled features as input and outputs a mask that is of the same size as the input region.

Sequential Image Analysis: Sequential image analysis models can be used to forecast eddies occurrence. Given a set of sequence SSH images

for the field, the task is to predict the eddies for the future based on the temporal resolution of the dataset. For this task, we used sliding window techniques to build a sequence of 30 days lag as shown in Figure 8. Then we explored the performance of different models on predicting the future eddies for (1) day ahead and for (7) days ahead.

Figure 8: Sliding window technique, presented using a sequence daily image. Each image in the sequence represents a single time step. we generate sequences by moving the input window one-time step at a time across the entire available data sequence.

We first used LSTM networks, which are shown to be very effective in modelling long-term dependencies in sequential data. The architecture of an LSTM network typically consists of multiple layers of LSTM cells, with each layer learning increasingly complex representations of the input sequence. The final layer typically outputs the prediction or classification for the entire sequence. We also used a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), which is the main method used for image classification and recognition. CNN consists of multiple layers of filters that are applied to the input image to extract important features. Furthermore, as our data consists of sequential data with a spatial component, we test a hybrid model that combines both LSTM and CNN. The result for each model is presented in the later sections.

Semi-supervised Models: Given that labelled SSH maps are very expensive datasets, the field suffers from having a lot of unlabelled data, thus affecting the applicability of supervised models. Therefore, we decided to explore the use of semi-supervised learning (SSL) approaches. Several SSL semantic segmentation models have been developed for the biomedical field [29], and other "consistency training" methods based on noise injection (Gaussian noise, drop-out noise or advanced image augmentation), have also been developed [30], [31].

Here, we explored the application of such published SSL models for eddy detection. However, they were generated for "traditional" images that have pixel channel values (e.g. the cifar-100 dataset), and are not straightforward to modify to deal with SSH map "images" which are made from one SSH channel value.

We finally adopted the idea of a semi-supervised self-training model as shown in Figure 9. It is one of the simplest methods of semi-supervised learning. We will first apply data augmentation on both labelled and unlabelled datasets, to get a large amount of data. Second, the trained Mask-RCNN model would be used to generate predictions on the unlabelled data, where the predictions are considered pseudo labels. Lastly, the most confident pseudo labels would be extracted and combined with the labelled dataset to retrain the model. This approach is expected to improve the generalisability of the model and minimize the effect of over-fitting.

Figure 9: Three stages of the adopted semi-supervised self-training method. First, a baseline model is trained on a small training labelled dataset. Then the model is run on a large unlabelled dataset and the best-segmented images are identified by visual checks. Finally, we pool the original labelled dataset with the best segmented unlabelled images and train a new model with them.

3.2 SSH mapping: Task A

3.2.1 Vector-Field-Based Identification of Oceanic Eddies

The interpolated SSH data are used to generate a vector field. Consider a flow on the plane with velocity field (our desired vector field) $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{X}, t)$, where $\mathbf{X} = (x, y)$ denotes position and t is time. We are concentrating here on one fixed time and just on spatial changes in SSH. The vector field $v(\mathbf{X}, t)$ thus is assumed to be of the form

$$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{X}) = \frac{g}{f} \left[\frac{\partial \eta(\mathbf{x})}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial \eta(\mathbf{X})}{\partial x} \right] \quad (1)$$

here $\eta(\mathbf{X})$ denotes SSH; f is the Coriolis parameter (twice the local vertical component of the earth's angular velocity); and g is the acceleration of gravity [32]. Figure 10 illustrates two view styles of vector fields generated.

We then generated a vector field from SSH values, the critical points need to be found and the three types of critical points (those in Figure 5) need

Figure 10: The generated vector field and its streamline visualisation

Figure 11: The generated vector field and its identified critical points. For better visualisation, all vectors are shown with the same magnitudes. Different colours indicate different magnitudes.

to be identified. As can be seen in figure 11, the blue dots represent the critical points in the generated vector field. Comparing this plot with the eddies map, it is evident that exists a good correlation.

3.2.2 Physics Informed Neural Networks

We began with a very basic Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) structure, with two linear layers and ReLU activation between the two. We had the same number of neurons in each layer. We used the Adam optimiser, and initially, due to computation and time constraints, we only trained over 2 or 3 epochs to get initial results.

Our implementation of the vector field derivation used the finite difference numerical method (Taylor's theorem) to find the derivatives from the SSH at each point. We compared our implementation of the vector fields to that produced by py-eddy-tracker for the same input SSH map, to check if it was creating accurate vector fields. We had to implement our own version in Pytorch for the model to use as a loss so that it could calculate the gradients through the loss function. We compared the vector fields from our implementation with that of the py-eddy-tracker and we observed a good match as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Vector fields from current work and py-eddy-tracker

Initial Experiments – 7-day window period: We began with a 7-day sliding window of input data, so the input data contained the satellite data from all 4 satellites on days 1 - 7. We then attempted to interpolate the map for day 7. An example of the 7-day input is shown in Figure 13a. We used the eNATL60 NEMO ocean model data as the target data. Our first models used the traditional RMSE (root mean square error) loss function, to test

whether our models were working as expected so we could get a baseline to compare the physics-based Helmholtz loss against later on.

For the 7-day experiments, we had a total of 303 input/target pairs and used a train/test/validation split of 242/30/31.

Figure 13: Input and predicted output of the basic MLP model with 7-day window input, 2 epochs of training and the traditional RMSE loss function.

Figure 14: Target SSH map for 7-day initial test.

Figure 13b shows the initial results we achieved with the basic MLP. They show promise, with some features of the target (shown in Figure 14) becoming apparent. We decided to continue investigating the basic MLP,

with the Helmholtz loss but also investigating the performance (1) when using a denser input by using a 28-day sliding window and also (2) including more explicit time information in the input.

Initial Experiments – 28-Day Window Input Data: We looked at the effect of increasing the sliding time window to 28 days of data. One can do this without worrying about the eddies being lost as mesoscale eddies typically last about a month. The 28-day input is shown in Figure 15b as an example, which can be compared with the 7-day input in Figure 15a to demonstrate how much this reduces the sparsity in our input data, with a potential for improving the performance. For the 28-day inputs, we had a total of 276 input/target pairs and used a train/test/validation split of 220/28/28.

Figure 15: Inputs for 7-day and 28-day window period. The color scale represents the normalised sea surface height (SSH).

The output of the basic MLP with the traditional RMSE loss of the SSH maps only is shown in Figures 13b and 16a for the 7-day and 28-day respectively. The 28-day output is starting to show more of the features of the target output shown in Figure 17, which is a promising start especially where this is the output after only a single epoch of training. In particular, Figure 16a has some clearer eddies in the grid space between 45 – 50 longitude and -60 – -55 latitude.

Helmholtz Loss - Initial Experiments: Our initial experiments with

Figure 16: Predicted output using RMSE and Helmholtz loss using 28-day window period input using basic MLP and only 1 epoch of training.

Figure 17: Example target for the outputs shown above

Helmholtz loss showed that the Helmholtz loss might improve the model, as more detail is starting to become apparent along the border between the blue and red sections in Figure 16b.

Further Experiments with more epochs: We were able to increase the computational capability available to us, in particular gaining access to GPUs which greatly sped up our training. Due to this, and the initial promising results we had, we began more extensive training, over ten epochs with each of the models.

The traditional model has drastically improved, with Figure 18a showing the output of the model and Figure 19 showing the target SSH map. In fact, even the 7-day window data had similar outputs, which would indicate that overfitting may be occurring. We put in place a few measures to try to limit overfitting, such as shuffling the data (after the input windows were combined into one input) between the test, train and validation datasets. Additionally, we used the validation dataset to determine the best model during training. However, we had very limited data, with less than 250 inputs, and all of the data was from the same region over a continuous ten-month period. As mentioned before, mesoscale eddies last around a month, so ten months of continuous data will not provide much variety to train on. All of these factors may have led to the model overfitting. The best validation loss from training was 0.0994 on epoch 10, and the average loss on the test dataset was 0.0429 which is approximately half of the training loss. This is another indicator that overfitting may have occurred.

Figure 18: Predicted output using RMSE and Helmholtz loss using 28-day window period input using basic MLP and 10 epochs of training.

Further training of the Helmholtz model shown in Figure 18b shows that it smooths out the SSH map more than before, but does not improve much overall when compared with the target in Figure 19. The best validation loss from training was 0.2233 on epoch 5, and the average loss was 0.1211 on the test dataset. The loss comprises of the SSH output RMSE loss and the Helmholtz/Vector Field loss, and the drop in loss may be an indicator of some level of overfitting similar to the basic model with only

Figure 19: 28-day target SSH map for the models with 10 epochs of training.

RMSE loss. Figure 20a shows the vector field plot for the model's output, and Figure 20b shows the vector field plot for the target SSH map. There are elements of the vector field starting to resemble the target vector field. Fine-tuning of the balance between the RMSE loss of the SSH and the Helmholtz loss could be beneficial to investigate further, as due to limited time-frames we were unable to investigate this fully. This may balance the benefit of the RMSE loss which seems to help smooth out the map, with the potential benefit of the Helmholtz loss reducing the overfitting potential.

Time Information – Some Experiments: We decided to add an extra channel of information on the input, with the time information from the simulated satellite data in seconds. The addition of the time in the input did not impact the traditional MLP model much, but it may have reduced the effects of overfitting slightly, as there are features in the target map in Figure 22 which are not present in the output shown in Figure 21a, such as the red area at around (-53, 51). The best validation loss during training was 0.1062 at epoch 10, with a trend of the loss declining over all the epochs, and the average loss on the test data was 0.0418 which is again about half the loss from training.

For the model using the Helmholtz loss, the addition of time information seemed to greatly improve the model's performance. Figure 21b shows the output, with the target data being shown in Figure 22. This output is

(a) 28-day Helmholtz vector field output (b) Vector field output for the target SSH map

Figure 20: Predicted vector field outputs using RMSE and Helmholtz loss using 28-day window period input using basic MLP and 10 epochs of training.

(a) 28-day with time-RMSE output example (b) 28-day with time-Helmholtz loss output

Figure 21: Predicted output using RMSE and Helmholtz loss using 28-day window period input using basic MLP and 10 epochs of training with embedded time information.

very similar to that of the model based solely on RMSE loss, with one notable difference being the texture across the map, which is slightly reminiscent of the satellite tracks which may be an artifact of how we provided the time data to the model. The difference in the outputs with

Figure 22: Target SSH map for the models using time data with 10 epochs of training.

the time data to that shown in Figure 18b indicates strongly that the addition of time information is beneficial to the model. The best validation loss during training was 0.2918 on epoch 7, with an average loss of 0.1329 on the test dataset. Figures 23a and 23b show the vector fields of the Helmholtz loss output and the target respectively. The output vector field again shows a drastic improvement with the addition of time information for the case with the Helmholtz loss model. In summary, utilising the physics of the problem in the machine learning model training shows promise in developing a generalised model to obtain an accurate SSH map.

3.2.3 Auto-encoder experiments: Data pre-processing

The main aim was to generate along-track altimetry and sea surface height maps for training a variational autoencoder. A common problem with altimetry interpolators is the irregularity in the generated sea surface height. To make the SSH output smoother, we added a (\vec{u}, \vec{v}) based penalty term in the loss function. To generate the (\vec{u}, \vec{v}) terms, we utilised the stencil method as mentioned in the documentation of 'py-eddy-tracker' [33]. However, the python package used the Absolute Dynamic Topography instead of the sea-surface height. We needed the

(a) 28-day Helmholtz vector field output (b) Vector field output for the target SSH map

Figure 23: Predicted vector field outputs using RMSE and Helmholtz loss using 28-day window period input using basic MLP and 10 epochs of training embedded with time information.

actual height to convert SSH to ADT, which was calculated using the Earth Gravitational Model 2008 (egm2008.pgm) [34]. According to Figure 24 below, the Absolute Dynamic Topography can be calculated by $ADT = SSH - h_{adt}$ [35].

Figure 24: SSH to ADT conversion. A) Relationship between SSH and ADT [35], B) h_{ADT} over the dataset's lat/lon bounds

To calculate (\vec{u}, \vec{v}) from the ADT field, we can use the geostrophic balance equation, which relates the horizontal pressure gradient force to the Coriolis force:

$$\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x} = -\frac{1}{\rho f} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y}$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{\rho f} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x}$$

Where η is the SSH, ρ is the density of water, f is the Coriolis parameter, and p is the pressure. Assuming that the flow is purely horizontal and incompressible, we can use the continuity equation to relate the horizontal velocity components u and v to the pressure gradient:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0$$

Using the first two equations above, we can eliminate the pressure gradient and obtain expressions for u and v in terms of the SSH:

$$u = -\frac{g}{f} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial y}$$

and

$$v = \frac{g}{f} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x}$$

where g is the acceleration due to gravity.

We used the 5-point stencil method to calculate the derivatives. Figure 25 shows the UV vector field visualised in different ways.

For merging the along-track altimetry, we used a sliding window of 6 days with an overlap of 3 days. In total, we had 565 combined altimetry records and 275 corresponding SSH maps from the model. The figure 26 shows the final output.

3.2.4 Training Setup

Loss function

Detecting mesoscale eddies requires an optimally interpolated vector field of the sea surface heights. To achieve this, we investigated a novel loss

Figure 25: (Left) The vector field overlaid on top of the ADT field, (Top-right) The vector field visualised with a stream plot, (Bottom-right) The angle measure of the velocity field $\arctan2(\frac{v}{u})$

term which penalises the model based on the RMSEs of the \vec{u} and \vec{v} velocity components.

The interpolation loss consists of three terms. The reconstruction loss \mathbb{L}_{recon} , is the direct RMSE between the predicted and target sea surface heights, the novel term $\mathbb{L}_{(\vec{u}, \vec{v})}$, which calculates the RMSEs of the velocity components based on their magnitudes and angles, and the divergence term \mathbb{L}_{KL} , which is only used when training a variational auto-encoder,

$$\mathbb{L}_{interp} = \mathbb{L}_{recon} + \lambda \mathbb{L}_{(\vec{u}, \vec{v})} + \gamma \mathbb{L}_{KL}$$

where,

$$\mathbb{L}_{KL} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2 + \mu_i^2 - \log(\sigma_i) - 1$$

Figure 26: The Absolute Dynamic Topography from the along-track merging and the corresponding dense model

$$\mathbb{L}_{(\vec{u}, \vec{v})} = RMSE(\|\vec{u}_p, \vec{v}_p\| - \|\vec{u}_t, \vec{v}_t\|) + RMSE(\theta_p - \theta_t)$$

and

$$\mathbb{L}_{recon} = RMSE(SSH_p - SSH_t).$$

Since we are training from scratch, the λ and γ terms are used as weights in the loss function to prevent gradient explosion. In the experiments, λ and γ were kept same and had a value of $1e^{-10}$. The weights were kept this small to match the \mathbb{L}_{recon} range. Figure 27 shows the effect of scaling on the loss functions. In principle, as the loss measures have different magnitude ranges, scaling was applied in order to assign importance to each loss function.

Training hyperparameters The choices of hyperparameters were obtained with an initial guess of ranges as shown in Table 2. They were then optimised on a Stratified 2-fold train/test split.

Autoencoder model architecture The use of convolutional auto-encoders for altimetry to SSH interpolation is investigated. An auto-encoder consists of two main components; (encoder and decoder). The convolutional layers in the encoder are arranged to compress the input information with fewer and fewer parameters the deeper the input propagates. The decoder is a mirror image of the encoder. Thus, the hourglass topology allows the model to learn an informative latent space

Figure 27: Right (top and bottom) figures show The $\mathbb{L}_{(\vec{u}, \vec{v})}$ and \mathbb{L}_{recon} terms plotted (in vertical axis) as a function of $(\vec{u}_p - \vec{u}_t, \vec{v}_p - \vec{v}_t)$ and $(prediction, SSH)$, respectively. It can be seen that the two loss functions operate in different ranges with orders of difference in their magnitudes. Left figure shows the effect of applying scaling of $\lambda = 1e^{-10}$ to the $\mathbb{L}_{(\vec{u}, \vec{v})}$. The weighting acts as a homogenous transformation that shifts the loss landscapes into a common range domain without skewing their importance in \mathbb{L}_{interp} .

Z. The variational auto-encoders are different because their latent spaces are continuous. Instead, their latent space model the features near the neck as a normal distribution to sample from. The schematic of the autoencoder architecture is shown in Figure 28

Result I: Ablation

In the context of loss functions, ablation refers to removing or disabling a particular component of the loss function and observing the resulting change in performance. The goal of ablation is to gain insights into which components of the loss function are most important for the task at hand

Hyperparameter	Value	Remarks
Batch size	16	Could have been higher
Epochs	250	Arbitrary
Learning rate	$1e^{-2}$	The latent dimension was restricted to 50 to avoid overfitting, and L1 weight regularisation was used to penalise large gradient steps in the loss function.
Momentum	0.9	Arbitrary
Decay	$1e^{-3}$	Ensures weight regularisation
Gradient clip	1400	Prevents gradient explosion
$\gamma = \lambda$	$1e^{-10}$	The small value is because the reconstruction loss term operates in the (0, 1) range, and the other terms operate in (0, $1e^{+10}$) range.

Table 2: Hyper-parameters for training the Auto-encoder

Figure 28: The difference between the traditional auto-encoder and variational auto-encoder.

and identify potential improvement areas.

Figure 29: Ablation test for the Variational Auto-encoder with and without $\mathbb{L}_{(\vec{u}, \vec{v})}$ term.

In Figure 29, the Variational Encoder’s convergence during the training is plotted. The dashed line shows the training/testing loss values when the proposed UV loss term was not used. The solid lines show the loss values when the UV loss was included. The model converges much more quickly and finds a better latent landscape for interpolation. Figure 29 also illustrates the loss function without the UV term is easier to overfit because it keeps decreasing beyond the point of return; see epochs (80, 100); inset.

Result II: Interpolation artifacts, AE Vs VAE

Figure 30 visually compares the interpolation results for an auto-encoder and the variational auto-encoder. Both models have almost the same architecture, except for the additional fully connected layers of output size 100 in the VAE for estimating the parameters (μ, Σ) of a normal distribution (See the architectural diagram). The auto-encoder interpolation in the top-left (inset) has blocky artifacts due to the combination of large convolutions and discrete latent space. As the top-right figure shows, the variational alternative solves this issue and generates a much smoother interpolation because of its continuous

sampling strategy.

Figure 30: Visual comparison of the interpolation, AE Vs VAE

Result III: Interpolation over time

We also qualitatively assessed the VAE's capability to interpolate over time. We imagined time as an arbitrary variable to weigh the sum of the first and last week's altimetry. Therefore by increasing this weight over 173 intervals, we fed the model the combined altimetry and generated the prediction shown in the middle of Figure 31. Without any concept of time dimension during the training process, the model has learnt some notion of time, which can be studied further in future research.

Result IV: Spectrum analysis

We conducted a spectrum analysis to check if the model was able to capture the wavelengths present in the data. The results are presented in Figure 32. It can be observed that the model captured very well the wavelength characteristics in the data, showing the good interpolation achieved in the present results.

Figure 31: Interpolation over time

3.2.5 Convolutional Neural Networks

In this section, we present the CNN model details and the results of the SSH interpolation obtained from the trained CNN model.

CNN model architecture: The model architecture was mainly a result of ad-hoc experimentation. Due to constraints of the GPU memory and the large grid size required for the predicted images, we could not add many layers to the model that would explode the GPU memory. After some experimentation, we found that the above architecture worked well and allowed us to train within the constraints of the GPU memory. Further research in using CNNs can yield better results in predicting the SSH

Figure 32: The wavelengths captured in our model agree with those present in the data. This ensures that our interpolation method can accurately represent the SSH map at high resolutions. The model performs poorly in the (0.0, 0.1) range, which means low-scale features are disregarded. However, the performance of the model can be tuned by balancing the training data bias.

maps, which can be part of future work.

Figure 33: CNN Model Architecture

Apart from the GPU and memory considerations, the input data was also a main consideration. Large parts of the input images were empty which is why we chose large (50, 50) kernel sizes to have more relationships

captured between the input and ground truth.

Model training: The model was created using PyTorch and trained for 20 epochs on a Tesla M60 which took about 20 minutes of time to train with a batch size of 16. We also used a Train-Test split of 80-20 giving us around 431 images for training. The loss function used was the standard RMSE loss along with the Adam Optimizer. We also tried training for larger epochs but the model performance did not improve much. Due to time constraints, further experimentation on improving the CNN performance was not possible.

Model performance and predictions: Although we did not get to tune the hyper-parameters of the model, the model did give promising results even without much tuning. Some examples are shown below:

Figure 34: SSH map predictions of the CNN model. Also shown are the along-track input (left) for the model and the ground truth (right)

We can see from the above images that while the predictions do not exactly replicate the SSH ground truth, we start to see the model capturing trends across the SSH grid which look promising. However, it looks like the model is overfitting based on the training and validation losses observed. Hence it is suggested to use a more complex model architecture to better learn the input-output correlations.

In summary, the CNN model we used was a simple ad-hoc CNN but with a more robust architecture, training for longer, more data and potentially including a vector field loss, we believe the CNN model can deliver good performance on the interpolation task.

3.3 Eddy identification: Task B

3.3.1 Semantic Segmentation: Mask-RCNN model

For this part of the project, we utilised the pre-trained Mask-RCNN model (details of which are described earlier in Section 2) from the PyTorch library. Since we only needed to predict two classes (eddy and no eddy), we fine-tuned the model using a sample of 4000 training images that were randomly cropped and flipped (both horizontally and vertically), and a sample of 500 validation images. The tuning was performed on a single GPU-P100, which greatly accelerated the process, allowing us to process all the data samples in approximately twenty minutes. We observed that both the training and validation losses continued to decrease after ten epochs, while the validation loss remained relatively constant after a few more epochs. We believe that a more accurate study of the data and the models themselves could lead to better performance, however, the first training presented here showed promising results.

For the training, a data loader has been implemented, in order to load the data and pre-process it. The pre-processing has been performed to create PyTorch-tensor, specify the types of all the tensors (this is crucial because setting the model to double precision would have taken hours for a single epoch, while single precision reduced it to 20 minutes) and do some data augmentation to reduce the bias on the training data, such as cropping and flipping. To train the Mask-RCNN model, we need to identify all the objects in the target images, create a mask for each one, create the bounding boxes and label them. This is because the models require a list

of tensors as input and a list of dictionaries as targets.

The developed model performed reasonably well with an overall IoU (the ratio between the intersection and the union of labelled pixels) of approximately 73%, with a global accuracy (the ratio of pixels predicted correctly) of over 90% on the test dataset. This high accuracy is not surprising considering that the eddies are small and sparse in the regions, therefore most of the space is just background.

In Figure 35, we can see an example of the prediction obtained with the model compared to the ground truth. The plot on the left is an SSH image sample, where the absolute values of the sea surface height discrepancy from the mean are plotted. We took the absolute values as we do not distinguish between cyclonic and anti-cyclonic eddies. On the right, there is an overlap between the target mask and the predicted mask. The yellow pixels (values=15) are the correctly predicted eddies, while the greenish pixels (values=10) are the wrongly predicted and the blueish (values=5) are the eddies that have not been predicted.

Figure 35: Example of the segmentation results, compared to the ground truth (right) of an SSH map (left) from the EddyNet dataset. The mask on the right has three different values: 0, which refers to the background, 5, which refers to the ground truth that has not been predicted, 10, which is the wrongly predicted eddies, and 15 represents correct prediction

3.3.2 Semi-supervised + Self-training Approach

This approach makes use of results from our previous experiments: the simple image augmentation scripts, the mask-RCNN, and the unlabeled dataset generated from the eNATL dataset. Our baseline trained model on the EddyNet labeled dataset achieved a global accuracy of 0.74. When ran on an augmented version of the EddyNet dataset the accuracy dropped to only 0.25, highlighting it was a highly overfitted model (as noted before in the parallel work track where we optimized another Mask-RCNN model). We tried running the baseline model on the augmented unlabelled dataset we generated from the eNATL dataset for the same region as that used from the EddyNet dataset. However, due to the limited computational resources and the timeline for the DSG, we were not able to finish this run. The distribution of average pixel probabilities for the first batch of 100 images is shown in Figure 36.

From this distribution, we selected the threshold of 0.375 for a segmented image to be moved forward as most confidently segmented to be pooled with the original EddyNet dataset for the training of a new mask-RCNN. However, we did not have the required computer power to run this model in time, which can be a task for further research.

3.3.3 Sequential Image Analysis: LSTM-CNN Networks

In this section, we approached the dataset as a time series and attempted to model it and predict future eddies. An LSTM-CNN network is built and trained using the time-series data to make predictions of the eddies. Moreover, we also tried the LSTM model without the CNN layers. Using 100 epoch size, the Mean Squared Error (MSE) value for both models is presented in table 3. These two models were able to learn the temporal pattern of the data. However, due to time limitations, we ran each model only once. Therefore, it was hard to find out which model outperformed in the prediction task. For the 1-day ahead prediction, the LSTM model outperformed while for the 7-days ahead predictions, the CNN-LSTM model achieved a better performance. More research is needed in the direction to come to detailed conclusions.

Figure 36: Distribution of the average scores of the probability of a pixel of an image belonging to the eddy class for the segmentation.

Model	one day Prediction -MSE	7-days Prediction - MSE
LSTM	0.0682	0.0769
CNN-LSTM	0.0750	0.0733

Table 3: Test MSE value for LSTM and CNN-LSTM model trained on one-day prediction and 7-days prediction.

3.4 End-to-end pipeline: From along-track data to SSH mapping and eddy detection

For our final experiment, we attempted to create an entire pipeline using the two models that showed the most potential from the sub-projects in tasks A and B. In Figure 37, we can observe an instance of the produced SSH image and the predicted binary masks in comparison to the targets. We chose to use the physics-informed neural network to generate the SSH images and the Mask-RCNN to predict the binary mask. Although the SSH maps appear comparable at first glance, the binary masks are notably different. This outcome was expected since the two models were trained on distinct datasets, and this kind of data is extremely sensitive to space

and time. Therefore, it is quite ambitious to employ the model to forecast outcomes in a different space and time. In the end, we are satisfied with our accomplishment of connecting the two components of SSH mapping and eddy detection (Tasks A and B) and devising an end-to-end pipeline that can travel the entire distance, from creating the SSH images (from satellite data) to predicting the eddies' position.

Figure 37: Results of the Ensemble method. Top left: SSH map generated with the physics-informed neural network; top right: target SSH image; bottom left: generated mask of the predicted SSH image; bottom right: generated mask from the target. The binary masks have been generated with the Mask-RCNN model.

4 Summary, Conclusions and Limitations

The DSG project attempted to develop machine learning-based solutions for the detection of mesoscale eddy detection in oceans from satellite images of the sea surface. The satellite images provide information on the Sea Surface Height (SSH) which in turn provides information about the presence of eddies. However, typical satellite altimetry data of the

SSH are sparse and gridded with a low resolution of $1/4^\circ$, which leads to inaccuracies in eddy detection. In this project, as a first task, we explored ML-based approaches for mapping or interpolation of the low-resolution SSH map onto a high-resolution grid. After this crucial step, in the second task, we implemented ML algorithms for eddy detection on the ML-interpolated SSH map obtained in the first task. Combining these two tasks or modules, i.e., SSH mapping and eddy identification, results in an end-to-end ML framework for the detection of mesoscale eddies in oceans, providing a tool for oceanographic science research.

To this end, the main conclusions drawn from the project as well as the limitations and scope for future work are presented for the two tasks, i.e., SSH mapping and eddy identification.

4.1 Main Conclusions

4.1.1 SSH mapping

For the SSH mapping task, we primarily used physics-informed neural networks (PINN), variational autoencoders (VAE) and convolutional neural networks (CNN). The results obtained from all the above models show that high-resolution SSH maps can be generated with reasonable accuracy from sparse satellite data. Importantly, the key features of the ground truth SSH map were very well captured using the implemented models, which is crucial for eddy detection.

Our physics-based machine learning models showed great potential in meaningfully interpolating the sparse SSH data. Adding physics-based loss functions into the training of the neural networks through the Helmholtz equations, showed that meaningful interpolation can be achieved. It is also envisaged that more complex model architectures might prove to be efficient in SSH mapping. For problems involving physical phenomena such as the ocean dynamics considered in this work, utilising the underlying physical information or the governing equations in the training of ML models can lead to reliable and potentially efficient ML-based tools as opposed to usually black box ML models. The implementation of the variational autoencoder architecture using combined loss functions shows promising results in which the model was able to interpolate in the spatiotemporal space (both in time and space).

This offers opportunities for further exploration for SSH mapping in space as well as its evolution over time. Finally, the CNN model architecture that we implemented provided good predictions of the target SSH maps in terms of capturing the key features.

4.1.2 Eddy identification

For the eddy identification task, Region-based CNN (RCNN) and Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) coupled CNN architectures were implemented.

The Mask-RCNN architecture, trained on a single GPU-P100, resulted in a global accuracy of 90% for the detection of the eddies. However, given the small size of the dataset, the model was overfitting, especially due to the fact that eddies last for several days, therefore there was not a significant variance in the dataset. In other words, the dataset has to be long enough (time-wise) to contain many eddies for training the model which might include the formation of newer eddies. To overcome this problem, we used data augmentation by randomly cropping the images and flipping them both horizontally and vertically.

The model implementation based on LSTM (with and without CNN layers) was shown to be capturing the eddies reasonably well. Using the time-series data of the interpolated SSH maps, they learned the temporal patterns in the data. However, further research is needed in the eddy identification task.

4.2 Limitations

4.2.1 SSH mapping

The models based on physics-informed neural networks, variational autoencoders and CNN performed well in capturing the key features of the SSH map, however, when it comes to finer details, the models have to be refined further to enable accurate eddy predictions. Nonetheless, the three major models explored here, serve as an excellent starting point for further research.

A limitation of vector-field-based modelling is related to the critical points covering a relatively small area in grids. As a result, probably the model

will be unable to identify the smaller eddies. The approximation of vectors near boundaries is another challenge in vector-field modelling. A high error rate is present near the boundaries between the ocean and land, which results in a lot of false critical points.

4.2.2 Eddy identification

Currently, to the best of our knowledge, there are only two main Python packages for the detection of eddies: EddyNet [6], which is a U-Net-based model and python-eddy-tracker [5]. Therefore, we started by testing them, but their implementation was not optimal (the published code did not run in our hands). So we set out to develop other modelling approaches ourselves.

The labelled dataset is small in comparison to all the available unlabelled data, thus complicating the building of supervised models that would not overfit. There are several published pre-trained image segmentation models, but they can only be straightforwardly applied to other fields (such as biomedical imaging), thus they are not very portable. Thus, for the specific identification of eddies, it was necessary to build and train the models ourselves in a computationally expensive step.

In order to increase our dataset size for the unsupervised approach (which requires a large amount of unlabeled data), we had to combine two different published SSH map datasets (the SSL dataset from the eNATL60 to merge with the one from EddyNet). However, this was not straightforward, as not all datasets are annotated with latitude/altitude information so that identifying the regions across the different datasets was time-consuming. Another challenge was the different image sizes across the datasets and input models. We had to make sure to resize the images to the same number of pixels for Mask-RCNN to be able to run.

5 Recommendations and future work

5.1 SSH mapping

5.1.1 Physics-based neural networks

In general, more complex model architectures and detailed parameter optimisation are suggested to improve the model predictions in our studies. Furthermore, combining Neural Processes with our physics-based approach might combine the best of both worlds in reality-grounded meaningful interpolation/mapping of sea surface heights.

The following further ideas could be investigated in terms of vector-field analysis for the Physics-informed neural networks model:

- Using sparse SSH dataset, generate sparse vector fields and work on methods to have a reasonable interpolation of vector fields
- Estimating the vector field using defined seed points in the grid that take into account the behaviour of the critical points
- Adding a third space dimension when calculating the vectors to have a three-dimensional vector space
- A time-based approach, including time in the process of the vector-field generation and examining the dynamical behaviour of eddies (critical points)

5.1.2 Variational autoencoders

- Latent space analysis: It is essential to analyse the latent space of the VAE network. This can be done by the principal component analysis of the (μ, Σ) output from the variational AE, which should be a 100-dimensional vector. Other clustering methods can also be employed to visualise the latent space, such as T-SNE.
- Temporal training: Adding an LSTM layer after the VAE is a potential future research direction.

- GradCam: It is also important to analyse the network by looking at the gradients during a forward pass.
- It's easy to overfit: Due to a fixed lat/long domain, the model only sees a few samples during the training.
- Further ablation studies: The study presented in the report was only done on a simple train/test split. The real goodness of fit check would require re-running that experiment over a stratified k-fold with the date as the sampling criterion.
- Models: transformers, end-to-end, fixing py-eddy-tracker, trying out other trackers to generate more data
- Tiling: We can split the along-track data into tiles (imagine Google Maps). Then we can selectively train an even smaller interpolator. After a pass-through over all the tiles, we combine the outputs back. It can be difficult to optimise the edges of the tiles. However, enough literature exists to deal with the edge noise. One possible way to deal with this is Bessel band-pass filters, used in the 'py-eddy-tracker' package.

5.2 Eddy identification

Mask-RCNN yielded interesting results despite using a small amount of data. Improving the architecture, selecting the appropriate backbone, and implementing more data augmentation can enhance performance. It would be beneficial to train the model on a dataset that distinguishes between the two types of eddies and to check for detection imbalances. Due to computational expenses, the model was only trained for 10-15 epochs, but extending the training duration could yield more insights since both training and validation losses continued to decrease. Finally, a learning rate scheduler would definitely help the model to converge. The scheduler is already implemented but not used.

For the self-training step of our model, we developed a metric to select the images that had on average most of their pixels classified above a subjectively defined threshold. It would be ideal to implement a data-driven selection of the threshold in the future, and also to devise other metrics that could potentially better identify our most confidently

segmented images. We believe that Semi-Supervised Learning (SSL) can further improve eddy detection, especially when there is an extensive amount of unlabelled data. However, due to time constraints, we were unable to pursue this direction, but we have set up the framework for future work. Given enough time, the semi-supervised self-training could be executed in iterations, to continually add confident predictions to the training dataset and retrain the model. It is a promising approach to improve the model's generalisability and minimize the over-fitting problem. The adjusted Mask-RCNN can predict additional data from the unlabelled SSH maps, increasing the dataset fourfold. Ultimately, retraining the Mask-RCNN model with the complete dataset is the only necessary step.

6 Team members

Participants

M. Lisandra Z. Mendoza is a senior research scientist in the Computational Biology Department at Novo Nordisk Research Center Oxford. She contributed to this project by exploring the semi-supervised learning approaches, helping with the project management of the activities, writing sections of the report and providing feedback and reviewing the report.

Futoon. M. abushaqra is a PhD student at RMIT University Melbourne. She contributed to this project by analysing the data, exploring the forecasting task using different sequential image analysis approaches and writing different sections of the report.

Yunbei Ou is a PhD student at the University of Glasgow, in Urban Studies. She contributed to this project by exploring semi-supervised self-training approaches, writing sections and generating charts for the report, and representing team B to do the presentation.

Madeleine Dwyer is a PhD student at the University of Southampton, UK, with a research focus on including elements of Causal Reasoning into Reinforcement Learning techniques. She contributed to this project by considering how to improve the interpolation from sparse data to full

SSH maps, primarily focusing on the physics-informed neural networks.

Sima Farokhnejad is a PhD student at the University of Exeter, UK. Her contributions to this project include vector-field-based modelling of the SSH dataset and identification and classification of critical points in the vector fields that could be representative of eddies.

Asheesh Sharma He is a joint PhD student at the University of Bristol and the University of West of England, UK. His research takes a deep-learning approach to fully automate farm and wild animal welfare assessment with 3D camera technologies. He contributed to this project by studying Sea Surface Height interpolation with auto-encoders.

Yogendrasingh Pawar is a Risk Management Consultant in the Financial Services Domain. His interests lie in using his Machine Learning & Finance experience for Risk Management and Business Intelligence applications. He contributed to this project by exploring SSH interpolation from Along Track Satellite Data using Vector Field calculations, Convolutional Neural Networks and Neural Processes.

Giorgio Cerro is a PhD student in Machine Learning for Particle Physics at the University of Southampton, UK. He contributed to this project by exploring some supervised models for semantic segmentation, in particular, he focused on the Mask-RCNN model. He also contributed to pre-processing the data. He was also one of the two facilitators of the team.

Nikolai Juraschko is a PhD student at the University of Oxford and the Rosalind Franklin Institute. He contributed to this project as a facilitator, with a particular focus on task A and supporting the participants involved. He also contributed to the model explorations and model-architecture designs and was involved in writing and structuring the report, as well as reviewing it.

Principal Investigator

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materials design to property predictions and data-driven physical simulations. He is the Principal Investigator (PI) for the DSG Challenge.

Challenge Owners

Jake Cunningham is a Research Student in Machine Learning at UCL. He is the Turing Intern for this project and worked together with the DSG Group and also represented the Challenge Owner, National Oceanography Centre (NOC) in the project.

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